

Newsletter EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

09 July 2025, Edition 12

Questions to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (Q2E)

All Q2E answers are available [online](#).

- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2024-008](#): Piling behaviour Q2
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-002](#): Culling Individuals (ongoing)
- [Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-003](#): Second stunning of rabbits

→ The Q2E webform is available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/QuerywebformIQ3/questionnaire.htm>

→ You can download [here](#) the webform in PDF to prepare your Q2E submission.

Spanish webinar 02.06.2025

Last 2nd June 2025, a webinar in Spanish about Welfare assessment during electrical stunning in rabbits was held, with the support of the Catalonian Government, who promotes every year technology transfer sessions for the sector. It was a repetition in Spanish of the EURCAW webinar “Welfare assessment during electrical stunning in rabbits” held in 12.11.2024 in English. 60 participants from Spain were connected.

Recording of the webinar:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pQ3rXrBSxVg>

Link to the presentations pdf: [20250602_PATT HOES rabbits presentation.pdf](#)

Meeting the EU Member States Competent Authorities

→ The sixth EURCAW-Poultry-SFA EU network meeting will take place physically on 1-2 October 2025 on 2 *0,5 days at ANSES, Maisons-Alfort, France. This meeting will be the occasion for the Centre to exchange with the EU Member States Competent Authorities about their needs and priorities. A *world café* will be organized for knowledge sharing and discussion in small groups.

2025 Highlights

Four EURCAWs meeting

From 13-14 May, EURCAW Aqua hosted the annual meeting of the 4 EURCAWs in Heraklion. More than 40 professionals from all four EURCAWs (EURCAW Aqua, EURCAW Ruminants & Equines, EURCAW-Pigs, and EURCAW-Poultry-SFA) gathered to exchange knowledge, strengthen collaboration, and discuss future directions. A *World Café* to discuss topics such as how to improve the format of factsheets, quality assurance during the peer-review process, training initiatives and the community of practice was organized. The small group discussion continued, focusing on common activities across the EURCAWs such as roadshows and the development of an EURCAW App, communications, and training. Despite an earthquake in the early hours of Day 2, the meeting was a great success – facilitating fruitful discussions across the 4 EURCAWs.

© EURCAW-Aqua

★ Italian roadshow

© EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

© EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

The first EURCAW-Poultry-SFA Roadshow took place in Italy on 02 and 03 July 2025. The event was organized by the three Italian members of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA. The Italian central competent Authority (CCA) expressed its interest in the topic: animal welfare indicators collected at slaughter to assess welfare on farm, as this is key to the implementation of the Italian animal welfare annual control plan for poultry. The focal point of the CCA and a representative group of 23 veterinary officials responsible for official controls in poultry slaughter plants from the main poultry producing regions participated to the event. After welcoming and introduction of all participants the organizers gave an introduction and update of EURCAW-Poultry-SFA activities followed by a presentation of the EU Partnership activities related to the topics on indicators at slaughter for assessment of welfare on farm with particular focus on FPD (footpad dermatitis). The focal point of the Italian CCA presented the Italian National animal welfare annual control plan (PNBA 2024) and gave updates on related national poultry welfare legislation. Later, an icebreaker exercise on FPD scoring was administered to the participants and the results were discussed the following day. Two of the participants presented a report on data collection and evaluation at a slaughter-plant in their district (ASL Cuneo 1) which stimulated very interactive discussions on the type of welfare data collected at slaughter and how these are collected and analyzed. Other topics discussed were the verification of stunning equipment and fitness for transport. Finally, there was a debate on the use of EURCAWs outputs, how to improve dissemination and suggestions for future activities or topics for the EURCAW Work Program.

★ EURCAW-Poultry-SFA's tenth scientific article

The Centre is celebrating the publication of its tenth scientific article as a result of the work carried out in Activity 3 in 2023-2024.

The aim of this work was to study the impacts of a covered veranda on broiler chicken welfare.

This article named "*Positive impacts of a covered veranda on broiler chicken welfare*" has been published in Poultry Science and is available [here](#).

Latest documents published online

On-farm rabbit welfare

[Heat stress in rabbits](#)

Turkeys

[Use of sick pens in turkey farming](#)

Translations

[French](#)

[German](#)

[Italian](#)

[Spanish](#)

[Polish](#)

Co-funded by
the European Union

AARHUS UNIVERSITY

IZSLER

EURCAW Poultry SFA

European Union Reference Centre
for Animal Welfare *Poultry-SFA*

Newsletter: [Subscribe](#)
Email: info@eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu
Website: www.eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu